

A Short Note on the Comparison between the Tropospheres of Venus and Mars

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Introduction:

The two terrestrial planets Venus and Mars have a significant number of environmental differences and some very interesting atmospheric similarities.

Comparison	Mars	Venus
Planetary Surface Pressure (Pascal)	636	9,321,900
Planetary Surface Temperature (Kelvin)	211.8	699
Scale Height (Atmospheric thickness) (m)	10,900	15,080
Atmospheric Composition: CO ₂ by Volume %	95.1%	96.5%
Height of the Planet's Lit side Tropical Tropopause (Km)	62.0	63.43
Equation Temperature of the Planet's Tropopause (Kelvin)	134.4	224
Equation Pressure of the Planet's Tropopause (Pascal)	0.592	8,042
Z15: Planet's Vacuum Planet Equation Emission Height (Km)	1.6	71.06
Z15: Planet's Vacuum Planet Equation Emission Pressure (Pascal)	548.3	1,868
Venus Atmosphere to Mars Surface Pressure Equivalence Height (Km)	0	76.23
Venus Atmosphere to Mars Surface Pressure Equivalence Temperature (Kelvin)	211.8	208.27
Venus Atmosphere to Mars Tropopause Pressure Equivalence Height (Km)	62	>100

Table 1: Mars Venus Planetary Atmospheric Comparisons

The Differences:

Venus is closer to the Sun than Mars and therefore receives a greater solar radiation flux.

Venus is a slowly rotating world; Mars is a fast daily rotator.

Venus is more massive than Mars and therefore has a higher surface gravity.

At its base the atmosphere of Venus is a high-pressure, high temperature environment.

At its base the atmosphere of Mars is a low-pressure, low temperature environment.

Venus has a high planetary Bond Albedo and is therefore visibly bright and reflective.

Mars has a low planetary Bond Albedo and is therefore visibly dull and poorly reflective.

The exit to space thermal radiation emission height of Venus is in the planet's stratosphere at an elevation of 71 Km.

The exit to space thermal radiation emission height of Mars is in the planet's surface boundary layer at an elevation of 1.6 Km.

The Similarities:

Both Venus and Mars contain an abundance of carbon dioxide gas in their respective atmospheres (Venus 96.5%; Mars 95.1%).

Both Venus and Mars have an equivalent tropopause elevation (Venus 63.4 Km; Mars 62.0 Km) this is despite the massive differences in the pressure and temperature profiles of the two planet's tropospheres and requires explanation.

Venus and Mars: Atmospheric Comparison

Figure 1: Venus and Mars - Atmospheric Comparison

Discussion

The 71 km elevation thermal emission layer of Venus is in the planet's stratosphere at an atmospheric pressure of 1,868 Pascal, which is a higher pressure than the 636 Pascal surface pressure of Mars. Because the two planets have an almost identical atmospheric carbon dioxide content, it therefore follows that carbon dioxide gas content in the troposphere of Mars must be completely transparent to surface thermal radiation. This is because the low-pressure Martian

atmosphere is environmentally equivalent to the thermally radiant transparent stratosphere of Venus.

Consequently, the observed 211.8 Kelvin average surface temperature of Mars, which is 2 Kelvin above the thermal emission temperature of 209.8 Kelvin can only be ascribed to the action by dust absorbance of insolation over the lit hemisphere. Furthermore, the observed 17.5 Kelvin average surface diurnal range of Mars (Day 220 Kelvin; Night 202.5 Kelvin) can only be caused by adiabatic convection as the thermal radiant opacity of the carbon dioxide gas in the Martian troposphere is that of a fully transparent medium with no thermal radiant energy blocking capacity

Conclusion:

Just as there is no greenhouse gas thermal radiant opacity in the low-pressure stratosphere of Venus, there is for the same reason no atmospheric thermal radiant greenhouse effect in the low-pressure troposphere of Mars. The equivalence in height of the tropopause on these two distinctly different terrestrial planets is a manifestation of the action of tropospheric adiabatic convection in the carbon dioxide atmospheres of both Venus and Mars.

Sources:

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